

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A479

16 September 1996

OXICOA — TACIA

ADDENDUM

The correct dates for each of the flights
are as follows:-

475	9 September 1996
476	10 September 1996
477	11 September 1996
478	13 September 1996
479	16 September 1996
480	17 September 1996
481	19 September 1996

TACIA OXICOA AUG-SEPT 96 Flight Summary

Prepared by: Andrew Kaye and Hannah Richer

[1] A475 9/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 1 2 hr 40 min

A short test flight for the chemistry instrumentation was carried out. The ozone, peroxide and formaldehyde instruments performed well. PAN was found to be below the detection limit of the GC's. The CO instrument did not work well (showing a large variability in background measurements). After initial concerns about the NO background, the NO_x instrument was found to operate satisfactorily on the two available channels (NO and NO₂).

An anticyclone centred to the west of the UK provided possible TACIA type weather. However, delays, due to incomplete airworthiness certification, meant that there was insufficient time to search for plumes from the UK. However, a small local plume was encountered in the Bristol Channel (51.36N, 4.12E).

Data from this flight could possibly be used to validate emission data from South Wales.

[2] A476 10/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 2 4 hr 30 min

Instruments performed as in the previous test flight: The ozone, peroxide and formaldehyde instruments performed well. PAN was found to be below the detection limit of the GC's. The CO instrument did not work well (showing a large variability in background measurements). The NO background had improved and the NO_x instrument was generally found to operate well on the two channels (NO and NO₂). However, on reaching maximum altitude difficulties were encountered on controlling the flow rate in the NO₂ channel.

A persistent anticyclone centred to the west of the UK again provided TACIA type conditions. However, delays, due to instrument requirements, meant that there was limited time to search for plumes from the UK. However, cross wind runs were carried out at an interval of approximately 60 miles along the SW coast. Trajectory analysis is to be carried out to determine whether the same air mass was sampled twice. However, no particularly notable plumes could be distinguished from the ozone, carbon monoxide and formaldehyde data. However, useful background information was obtained.

[3] A477 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight 6 hr 00 min

The presence of an occluded frontal system over Norway/North Sea facilitated the study of three different airmasses.

Profiles were successfully flown on both sides of the warm front, but there was not sufficient time to travel to the northern edge of the cold frontal surface. However the lowest levels of the second stack may have been north of the front.

Ozone, formaldehyde and PAN instruments worked well, but the CO background problem was not corrected and the NO_x NO₂ channel flow problem had not been resolved.

[4] A478 11/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 3 2 hr 56 min

Thursday 12 September was used to install the NO_y converters and rectify the CO instrument. The CO work was successful. However the NO_y converters took longer than expected to complete. This resulted in a delayed take off.

Although primarily a TACIA instrument test flight the opportunity was taken to characterise the Arctic Maritime air mass over the North Sea. This effectively completed the work started on A477.

The chemistry kit performed as well as could be expected given the reduced warm up times available. The ozone pump switched off unexpectedly during the flight which caused a loss of data until the problem was identified.

[5] A479 11/9/96 TACIA 5 hr 40 min

There was a high pressure centred over the North Sea on this day which gave rise to continental outflow in the south-west approaches.

A very successful trial of the TACIA flying pattern, with two stacks being flown to sample continental air. A double inversion (875 and 950 mbar) was identified effectively capping pollutants and isolating them from the ocean surface sinks. Elevated levels of aerosol, CO (170 ppb), NO (40 ppt), NO₂ (400 ppt) and O₃ (65 ppb) were noted in this layer. Another interesting parcel of air was also sampled at higher altitudes (6 - 8 km). This air parcel was characterised by high levels of CO and aerosol. All the chemistry instrumentation performed well and the flight will provide a valuable contribution to the TACIA experiment.

[6] A480 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight 6 hr 04 min

An anticyclone was centred to the north of the North Sea, such that continental plumes from northern Europe were reaching southern England across the North Sea. The same anticyclone was investigated during flight A479, at which time the high was centred over the UK.

The aim of this flight was to characterise air parcels within the anticyclone: both air parcels with recent continental influence and those with mainly marine back trajectories were studied. The highest pollutant concentrations of the campaign were measured during this flight in the boundary layer near Boscombe Down and in the marine boundary layer in the southern North Sea.

The marine boundary layer was distinct from the rest of the troposphere by a low level inversion. A slightly higher inversion was also apparent in profiles carried out north of 54 N. Interestingly, the seemingly typical vertical structure was not found in the southern North Sea: only the marine inversion was present.

A plume was encountered in the marine boundary layer at the first sampling region and elevated NO_x, NO_y and CO were observed with a corresponding decrease in ozone, indicating recent anthropogenic inputs. Profiles throughout the lowest 6000 ft of the atmosphere, whilst travelling northward, indicated some chemically aged parcels of air with elevated ozone, CO and NO_y. Haze layers were also visible. However, most of the air was generally clean. Further North, haze layers were less frequent, but layers with elevated ozone were still apparent. Elevated CO with a corresponding decrease in ozone indicated some recent pollution in the marine boundary layer at 57.2 N and 0.8 E.

All the chemistry instruments performed well during the flight. In particular, the peroxide measurements were found to show similar features to the calculated peroxide. Pitch, roll and yaw manoeuvres were carried out in order to test the NO_x inlets: preliminary results indicated that there were no large effects.

[7] A481 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight/NOXY test 6 hr 16 min

An attempt was made at an airmass characterization flight. However, within an hour of take off, the peroxide and CO instruments had failed completely and the NO_x was only functioning at 50%. After consultation with the instrument operators it was decided that useful tests could still be carried with the operational NO_x channels and the flight plan was changed to a NO_x test flight. Several NILU and MRF bottles were also filled for analysis of hydrocarbons and possibly CO.

However, it is interesting to note that, at one point, air of stratospheric origin was encountered: we were frustrated by the lack of a complete suite of instruments. Recently polluted air and air which was chemically aged, as indicated by ratios of NO_x/NO_y and ozone, were both sampled. Useful data on emissions from north eastern Europe may have been gained.

FLIGHT FOLDER

DATE: 16 / 9 / 96 TAKE OFF 1045Z H(local time) FLIGHT NO. A479
LANDING 1625Z

PROJECT OFFICER :

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST: A KAYE

FLIGHT LEADER: M. RULE

OBSERVER: 2D: M. PICKERING

OTHERS: NOXY: K. DEWEY / SBAQUITTE
CO: S. KESSLER / R GEBIG

PAN/OZONE: J. KENT

BOTTLES: D. TIDDEMAN

PEROXIDE: B. BANDY

FORMALDEHYDE: L. GARDINAS

+ J. FOOT

CAPTAIN: O'BRIEN

CO-PILOT: M. PURSE

NAVIGATOR: J. CANNING

ENGINEER: K. QUICK

LOADMASTER: J. AYES

TRIALS INSTRUCTION (3):

OPERATING AREA:

S.W. APPROACHES

GENERAL SYNOPTIC SITUATION:

TIME:

ACSOE / TACIA Campaign

A479 16th September, 1996

Start TIME (EM)	End TIME (EM)		HEIGHT	HDG
100620		Take off from BOSCOMBE		
110324 (13)	-113803 (14)	Run 1	FL180	250 deg
114849 (15)	-121640 (18)	Profile P1	FL240->50ft	210/090 deg
122340 (19)	-123750 (20)	Run 2	600ft	090/255 deg
124329 (22)	-131326 (23)	Run 3	2600ft	095 deg
131515 (24)	-133014 (25)	Run 4	600ft	265 deg
Porpoise Run				
133136 (26)	-133648 (27)	Profile up	100ft->5000ft	355 deg
133648 (27)	-134203 (28)	Profile down	5000ft->100ft	355 deg
134203 (28)	-134714 (29)	Profile up	100ft->5000ft	355 deg
134714 (29)	-135238 (30)	Profile down	5000ft->100ft	010 deg
135238 (30)	-140248 (31)	Profile up	100ft->FL100	015 deg
140248 (31)	-141349 (32)	Profile down	FL100->50ft	250 deg
141618 (33)	-143117 (34)	Run 5	2600ft	255 deg
143448 (35)	-150445 (36)	Run 6	4500ft->4000ft	090 deg
150723 (37)	-151223 (38)	Profile P2	5000ft->2600ft	250 deg
151223 (38)	-152524 (39)	Run 7	2600ft	250 deg
152836 (40)	-154753 (41)	Profile P3	50ft->FL180	110 deg
155006 (42)	-160501 (43)	Run 8	FL180	110 deg
162705		Land at BOSCOMBE		

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms:	Form Title
5	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet
1	Aircraft Scientist log
1	Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements
	Interactive log
1	Flight Leader pre-flight check form
2	Flight Leader in-flight check form
2	Flight Leader in-flight log
2	Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
	MCR log
	CCN log
	MARSS log
1	Chemistry log <i>ECA C</i>
1	Bottle Samplers log
	Particulate/Filter boom Operator's log
6	2DK/FSSP/Holography Operator's log
	Sonde Ejector's log
1	Navigator's log
	Photographic log (photocopy original)
1	Instrument status forms
✓	RTD prints
✓	Raw data plots
	Signal register
	Weather charts
	Satellite pictures
	Omega track (GPS)
	Electronics pre-flight
	Mechanical fit

A479 16-SEP-96 11:03:24-16:05:01GMT

INS TRACK - RUN NO.

Testing Atmospheric Chemistry in Anticyclones

SORTIE OBJECTIVE

Measure chemical composition of a polluted plume at different distances from land (i.e. as it degrades).

LOCATION:

SW Approaches. Travelling North West with the wind, crossing flight regions to be discussed with navigator.

WEATHER:

Anticyclonic conditions. Avoid areas of cloud and precipitation where possible.

FLIGHT PATTERN:

- [1] Depart Boscombe Down and transit to sampling area at convenient altitude.
 - [1.1] Hold climb at 3000 ft for wet chemistry check.
 - [1.2] 15 minute run (above boundary layer, speed not critical) for NO_x Calibration. FL 180
- [2] Profile descent from approx. FL240 at 1000ft/min to approx. FL70 then 500ft/min to minimum safe altitude.
- [3] Start horizontal runs, perpendicular to the wind, at altitudes determined by aircraft scientist.
- [4] After completion of horizontal runs transit for approximately 50 miles to the next sampling area.
- [5] Profile between approx. FL100 and minimum safe altitude at 500ft/min.
- [6] Start horizontal runs, perpendicular to the wind, at altitudes determined by aircraft scientist.
- [7] if time allows repeat [4],[5] and [6].
- [8] Sawtooth across wind into and out of the boundary layer (3 or 4 complete cycles).
- [9] Profile from minimum safe altitude to FL240.
- [10] Transit to Boscombe Down.
 - [10.1] 15 minute run (above boundary layer, speed not critical) for NO_x Calibration.

OTHER REQUIREMENTS:

Cabin pressure to be kept constant on level runs.

Height (metres)

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: TACA Date: 6/19/196

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kauge J. Foot

Flight No: A479 Page 1 of 3

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
					Latitude	Longitude		
10:52:43		TRANSIT	7.00	247	59.07	-3.20	5/8 cu below thin Ci above. haze below cu.	
10:57:05		TRANS	12.2	245	50.99	-2.00	3/8 cu below. no cloud over sea, thin Ci above. but very haze.	
11:02:13		TRANS	17.2	246	50.88	-3.07	Very Hazy 1/8 cu over land clear over sea. some ci above.	
11:03:26		R1s	180	246	50.85	-3.21	very little cu below cluster of cu ahead. very below clear above.	
11:09:50		R1	180	244	50.68	-3.80	Hazy no clear horizon cluster of 8/8 cu ahead over land.	
11:15							cu patch, extend run	
11:17:37		R1	180	247	50.49	-4.56	cluster of 8/8 cu below haze but cloud free elsewhere below clear above.	
							Second pulse of Noy and extend run again	
11:24:04		R1	180	236	50.31	-5.18	very haze 4/8 cu no cloud over sea clear above.	
11:29:55							overhead low cloud. haze below clear to south haze to west. clear above.	
							Aerosol increase increase with CO and ozone. @ 11:31	
11:38:08		R1c	180	194	49.66	-5.93	Hazy below clear above. some clouds on western horizon.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: FACIA

Date: 16/19/16

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye J. Foot

Flight No: A479

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
11:48:47	15	P1s	240	FL	247	49.25	-6.50	hazy and ^{cloud free} below white caps on sea. cloud ahead on horizon.	
11:53:54			19.1	FL	250	49.16	-6.95	line of haze visible extending from just ahead of AC to Port horizon.	
								15600 possible splice printed aerosol with ^{insufficient} _{particle} not on anyone.	
12:00:37		P1	12.1	FL	249	49.07	-2.66	high level cloud ahead associated with front to west haze with some ^{scattered} _{cu} or near surface.	
								10600 large increased aerosol.	
								7500	
12:06:23			4700					→ 5200 pt/min. 5200 peak in Aerose. ^{1000mb} _{height}	
								2000 cu tops. 1500 pt.	
12:16:44	18	P2c	50	R	484	49.15	-7.52	hazy a few cu above.	
12:23:06	14	R2	600	R	245	49.21	-6.98	hazy Sea state 4-5. (1228)	
								12:32 50 ppt NO.	
								1000 at start 600 now.	
12:37:22	20	R2e	600	R	247	49.01	-8.17	edge of Sc sheet very hazy.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: A-Kaye J. Foot

Project: TACV

Date: 10/11/66

Flight No: A479

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:43:29		R3	2600	R	2	48.95	-8.43	in cloud ask for zeros once out of cloud.	
								12:57:25 < NO 40 ppt NO 400 ppt 200-300 ppt NO 2	
12:59:56		R3	2600		88	49.18	-7.24	hazy dark brown band on horizon no clouds.	
								(13:04) CO dropping all NO ₂ falling. H ₂ O, rising across falling.	
13:13:26		R3	2600		82	49.30	-6.25	end of run very trend real.	
13:15:15		R4	600	R	251	49.26	-6.33	much more turbulent at this level, hazy no cloud. Sc deck to west.	
13:30:14		R4	600	R	251	49.09	-7.46	very hazy no cloud visible. some cu shadows on sea.	
								SCIG CO dropping at 136.30 198.82	
								13:37:06	
								13:40:16 1900 ft. top of marine layer. Some cu at this level.	
								2100 ft " " " "	
								(2600) 5300-5500	
14:02:48		R3	1000	FL				280 4000ft. 1200 (6700ft.)	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: TRACIA

Date: 16/9/16

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kenye & J. Foot.

Flight No: A474

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GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
14:13:49		P2e	50	R	241			1015 sea state 7	
14:16:18		R5	2600	P	239	51.30	-8.60	hazy some c: above. At PERSIP 600 gradual climb through sun	
14:26:02		R5	2600	P	244	51.15	-9.44	5/8 cu below edge of front	
14:31:16		R5e	2600	P	244	51.09	-9.87	in a layer.	
14:37:45		R6	4500	P	79	51.09	-9.89	approaching edge of Cu field clear & hazy ahead.	
								NO_y NO _y Most of NO _y in NO _x . NO ₂ 2ppt.	
14:45:								possibility Rm is just above "inverting layer" lot of discussion on PA. decide to stay course.	
								14:52 NO _y drop NO ₂ levels much higher 600 ppt.	
14:55								NO _x levels now falling slowly.	
14:57:30								EBOT rising again. ozone ↓ aerosol ↓	
15:01:19								NO _y & NO _x levels are stable No Drop to 4K ppt last 5min	
15:04:		R6c	4000	P	68	51.53	-7.24	scattered cu below clear above.	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: TACIA Date: 16/9/196

Aircraft Scientist: A. Kaye J. Foot

Flight No: A479 Page 5 of 5

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
15:07:23		P2	5000	P	245	51.57	-7.12	scattered cu below $\approx$ 4800 ci ahead and deck of Sc in distance.	
15:12:26		P2/R2	2600	P	244	51.49	-7.55	3600 at top of inversion 880mb. Sharp rise in NOy.	
15:15:30	39	R7	2600	P	244	51.32	-8.64	ci above. cloud ahead.	
15:23:30		R7						brown haze layer clearly visible.	
15:23:24	39	R7c	2600	P	244	51.32	-8.64	in brown haze layer.	
15:28:36	40	P3	50	R	100	51.34	-8.44	no cloud hazy SP — 1015 sea state - 7-8	
								sharp change PTEq @ 4Kft. 4800 $\leftarrow$ 880mb layer	
15:41:49	40	P3	120	P	103	51.27	-7.35	clear above at & below <u>hazy</u> .	
15:47:53	41	P3c	18000	P	107	51.23	-6.78	hazy no clouds.	
15:50:07	42	R8	180	FL	97	51.22	-6.51	warp drive run for NOy cal.	1629
16:05:01	43	R8e	180	FL	90	51.19	-4.45	end of run and science.	1630

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: A479

Date: 16.6.96

A/S Name: A. KAYE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for 3
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period indef
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project TASIA
4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? indef
5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in?
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A479 Date: 16.9.96 User: H RICHK
Interactive by: M. RICE
Date: 18.9.96

Renav

Applied Kalman filter

TWC

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : Profile / Whole flight / Other

$$a = - 0.3939 \text{ } \epsilon + 1$$

$$b = + 0.2589 \text{ } \epsilon - 2$$

$$c = + 0.5668 \text{ } \epsilon - 6$$

LWC

Heimann / Barnes

No corrections made.

Flight Leader's (Pre) In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A479 Date: 16. 9. 96

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GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0840	REF +	5	567			Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2855			Approx 3071 2858	
	AOSS	19	4095	PORT F/S STED O/S	TORQUE 2.0	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1666	F/S O/S	TORQUE 3.5	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	0			As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	3887	1010 / 0.1	1007 / 0.1	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3999	1005	✓		
	A/S	9	81	—		As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	110	343	341		
	UP2S	82	987	167	153		
	UHS	83	385	JNO	2		
	UP1Z	84	151	✓		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	145	✓		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	385	—	—	Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2493	+17	+16.4	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2527	+15		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0	—	—	As IAT	
	LP1S	91	386	94	94		
	LP2S	92	352	48	51		
	LRS	93	73	JNO	2		
	LP1Z	94	151	✓		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	156	✓		Approx 0148	
	LIRZ	96	74	—	—	Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2493	+19		As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2439	+20		As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0	—	—	As IAT	
	J/W	42	996	0	✓	As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47	—	—	—		
	HYGR	58	2938	14.6	14.8		
	HYCC	59	718	✓		696-901	
	FDEW	138	1982			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	608				
	DTF	10	255	16	✓		
	DTC	11	6				
	NDTF	23	90			same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	6	16	✓		
	INCT	48	—	—	—		
	GEN	140	2704	/ 2390		less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	2875	✓		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	175	✓		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	110				
	O3P	106	201			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	1495				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
0848	FL NO	1	Hex	479	✓		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	084	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	826	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	10	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
	LATC	160	Dec	4094			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4094			Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: *on the par*

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0849	TWCD	70	2900	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	1217	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	177	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2537	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2260	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2069	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2138	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1028	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4089	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	2043	✓			
	EV2V	171	2043	✓			
	NPWR	172	3357				
	EVIC	173	3968				
	EV2C	174	3968				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off/ On JND2	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off/ On JND2	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A479 Date: 16.9.96

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GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1057	REF +	5	567	✓		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2854	✓		Approx 2871 2858	
	AOSS	19	2178.	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	951	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	4095			As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	2369	FL134		As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3499				
	A/S	9	1289		180.	As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	2037.				
	UP2S	82	1794				
	UIRS	83	851				
	UP1Z	84	158	✓		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	156	✓		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	854			Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2756			As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2890			As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0			As IAT	
	LP1S	91	486				
	LP2S	92	485				
	LIRS	93	266				
	LP1Z	94	156.	✓		Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	172.	✓		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	265			Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2998			As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2947			As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0			As IAT	
	J/W	42	*934			As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47					
	HYGR	58	439		-34		
	HYCC	59	846	✓		696-901	
	FDEW	138	1206			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	993				
	DTF	10	2537		-14.6		
	DTC	11	4				
	NDTF	23	2318			same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	4				
	HNCT	48					
	CGN	140	2707	12392	HEIN.	less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	1228			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	1341			0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	152				
	O3P	106	1685			P ≈ (DRSU × 0.4) + 145mB	
	O3RG	113	1712				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
1107	FL NO	1	Hex	479	✓		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	111	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	006	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	13			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
	LATC	160	Dec	576	50.66 →		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4052		-3.84	Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: FL180

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1111	TWCD	70	1227	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2550	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1345	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2642	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2226	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	610	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	1514	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1022	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	3482				
	EV2V	171	3142				
	NPWR	172	2687				
	EVIC	173	4013				
	EV2C	174	3995				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A479 Date: 16.9.96

Page..2..of 2

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
1603	REF +	5	567			Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2854			Approx 2871 2856	
	AOSS	19	2178	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1927	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	4095			As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	1958		FL180	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3563				
	A/S	9	2263		235	As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	1167				
	UP2S	82	1036				
	UIRS	83	652				
	UP1Z	84	153	✓		Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	145	✓		Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	657	✓		Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	2899	✓		As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2916			As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0			As IAT	
	LP1S	91	278				
	LP2S	92	183				
	LIRS	93	210				
	LP1Z	94	149			Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	160			Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	210			Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	2900			As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2863			As IAT	
	LIRT	99	—			As IAT	
	J/W	42	1210			As Indicated 0000	
	NEPH	47	—				
	HYGR	58	1344				
	HYCC	59	835			696-901	
	FDEW	138	1208			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	929				
	DTF	10	123				
	DTC	11	5				
	NDTF	23	3921			same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	4				
	INCT	48	—				
	CON	140	2596	2392		less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	1243			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	1600			0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	0				
	O3P	106	0			P ≈ (DRSU × 0.4) + 145mB	
	O3RG	113	18				

FLIGHT LEADER'S IN-FLIGHT LOG

Date 16.9.96 Flight No. A479

Page 1 of 2

VIDEO TAPE

No. A479 #1
Ends 1345

- DFC
- RFC
- FFC

	GPS	INU
Lat.	50°33.20 N	50 32.68
Long.	4°15.61 W	4 1843W
Time	111513	111525

DRS recording to HORACE

HORACE recording to optical disk

SATCOM sending position reports

Time GMT	Event No	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.L Htr.		
074455		START	RECORD INU					GPS Pos		51°09.90N	
								Position		001°44.63W	
100535		SET	INU TO Navigate mode								
104620		TAKE OFF	FROM BOSCOM-OE								
104840		Start	Video								
			Climb up to FL180								
			START RUN 1 extend to do NAVY reboot and calibrate								
110326	13	FL180	—	255	180	238	-14.9	-33.2			
			END RUN 1								
113803	14	FL180	—	250							
			START PROFILE P1 ↓								
114819	15	FL240	—	210	180	270	-20.1	-30.9	OFF.	1000ft/min	
			descending cabin pressure slowly to -1000ft.								
			reduce r.o.d to 500ft/min								
			layer of increased aerosol cuts FL100								
120557	16	FL70	—	turn left, still descending							
120817	17		reduce r.o.d to 500ft/min								
			END PROFILE P1								
121640	18	50ft	1014	090			15.5	12.7		55	7/8

WCD 1200.

Port Equip
CD
P1
P2

Video Tape ok? 1345.

TIME GMT	EVENT NO	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.I. Htr.	wind °/ms ⁻¹
			START	RUN	2					
122340	19.	600ft	1014	090	180	183	13.7	10.3		
			END	RUN	2			just under	SCu	
123750	20	600ft	1014	255	180					
123809.	21	Heimann calibration (12 → 18).								
		carry on on same track for ≈ 4 mins then recip.								
			START	RUN	3		1/2 hr run.			
124329	22	2600ft	1014	090	180	188	10.5	10.3		162/22
125911		GPS Check		49° 09.06N	7° 17.33W					
125927		INU		49° 09.56N	7° 15.61W					
		Horace status ok.								
130129.		Satcom pos reports ok.					49 10.53	7 6.62		3 bottles filled
			END	RUN	3					
131326	23	2600ft	1014	095	180	180	10.5	1.9	OFF	152/20
			START	RUN	4					
131515	24	600ft	1014	265	180	184	13.9	2.0	OFF	127/14.
132720	—	HEIMANN Cal (12 → 18)					ST =	16.2		
			END	RUN	4					
133014	25	600ft	1014	265						
			START	POORPOSE	RUN					
133136	26	100ft	1014	355 355	170	172	15.2	12.4.		133/14
133648	27	500ft.	1014	355 355	180	194	8.6	c-4.1	OFF	160/16.
134203	28	100ft	1014	355	180	183	15.4	11.9		
134714	29	500ft	1014	355	180	182	10.3	-13.6.		
134830		Stop Video		A479 #1	counter 6122					
134840		Start Video		A479 #2	" 0000					

600 15
1500 30

1015/ht.

255.

ST 16.2

FLIGHT LEADER'S IN-FLIGHT LOG

Date 16.9.96 Flight No. A479

Page 2 of 2

VIDEO TAPE

No. A479.#2

Ends 1645

- DFC
- RFC
- FFC

	GPS	INU
Lat.	51°14.31'N	51°14.08'
Long.	8°57.58'W	8°59.43'
Time	142031	142045

DRS recording to HORACE

HORACE recording to optical disk

SATCOM sending position reports

Time GMT	Event No	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.I. Htr.		∅/ms ⁻¹	
135238	30	100ft	1014	010	182	182	15.4	11.0		PORPOISE RUN 7		
		2500ft	1014	015								
135907		GPS	Pos check		50°46.40'N							
					8°01.15'W							
135940		INU	"	"	50°48.35'N			8°01.38'W				
										PORPOISE RUN 7		
140248	31	FL100	1014	015	181	213	1.9	-24.7			160/20	
140815		Start	left turn onto 250, still descending									2600 5300 6700 5000
										END PORPOISE RUN		
141319	32	500ft	1015	250	180	186	14.4	11.2			7-55.	
										START RUN 5		
141618	33	2600ft	1015	250	183	193	11.3	3.2	OFF		160/20	
142807		In/out cloud										
										END RUN 5		
143117	34	2600ft	1015	255	188	195						
143448										START RUN 6.	30mins	
143448	35	4500ft	1015	090	182	198	18.9	-6.5				
150130		descending	to 4000ft to get back into plume.									
										END RUN 6		
150445	36	4000ft	1015	075	180							
		climb to		FL50							2600 150 29 mins FL25	
		START	PROFILE P2									500ft/min
150723	37	5000ft	1015	250	180	198	10.3	c-9.4	OFF		160/22	
										END PROFILE P2 /	START RUN 7	

Video Tape ok? 1645

TIME GMT	EVENT NO	HT	QNH	HDG	IAS	TAS	TAT	D.P.	D.I. Htr.		WIND
				END RUN	7						°/ms ⁻¹
152524	39	2600ft	1015	250	186	194	11.1	3.3	OFF		160 18
		descend to		50ft							
			START	PROFILE P3	↗						FL240 ✓50
152836	40	50ft	1015	110	180	185	15.1	10.0	OFF	7/8	FL150
1530		cabin		pressure							
				going							
				up.							
			END	PROFILE P3							
154753	41	FL240 FL180	110	110	182						
			START	RUN 8							
155006	42	FL180	—	105	18230	313	-15.4	-33.3	OFF		155 16
			END	RUN 8							
160501	43	FL180	—	110							
162705		LAND	AT	BOSCOMBE							
162945		stop	Video								
163221		stop	Recording							GPS Pos	51° 09.91 N
										Position	-001° 44.66 E

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No **A 479**.....

Project **TASIA**.....

Date **16.9.96**.....

Tape No **A479.#1**...

User **A. KAYE/H. RICHES**

Retention Period **indefinitely**.....

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
104840	6000	FEC	START RECORDING
110324 → 113803		"	RUN 1, FL150
114849 → 121640		"	PROFILE P1 V, FL240 - soft
122340 → 123750		"	RUN 2, 600ft
124329 → 131326		"	RUN 3, 2600ft
131515 → 133014		"	RUN 4, 600ft
133136 →		"	PORPOISE RUN 100ft → 5000ft
134830		"	END OF TAPE

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No **A** 479

Project TACIA

Date 16.9.96

Tape No A479 #2 User A.KAYE / H.RICHER

Retention Period .. indefinitely

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
134840	0000	FFC	START RECORDING
→ 141349		"	PARADISE RUN 100ft
141618 → 143117		"	RUN 5
143448 → 150445		"	RUN 6
150723 → 151223		"	PROFILE P2 ↓, 5000ft - 2600ft
151223 → 152524		"	RUN 7, 2600ft
152836 → 154753		"	PROFILE P3 ↑, 50ft - FL180
155006 → 160501		"	RUN 8
162705		"	Land at Boscombe
162945			Stop Recording

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT
 =====

FLIGHT NO: ~~A479~~
 A479

DATE: 16 / 9 / 196

MRF

INSTRUMENT	FITTED		OPERATED		COMMENTS
	YES	NO	YES	NO	
NAVIGATION: GPS OMEGA INU RADALT	/		/		
THERMOMETERS: DI TEMP NDI TEMP ICTP BARNES PRT4 HEIM	/		/		
HYGROMETERS: GEN. EASTERN TWC FWVS J/W	/		/		
EXP. PITOT HEAD: STATIC PRESS. PITOT PRESS. GUST VANES	/		/		
RADIOMETERS: UPPER CLEAR UPPER RED UPPER SILICON LOWER CLEAR LOWER RED LOWER SILICON MARSS MCR/SAFIRE DEIMOS	/		/		
CHEMISTRY: OZONE ECGC NOX	/		/		
OTHERS: CCN CLOUD PHYSICS CABIN PRESS NEPHELOMETER HOLOGRAPHY	/		/		

P.T.O. FAULTS/INCIDENTS

1. ER Monitor - No display preflight - white screen.
restart display / reset graph box.
2. NOx4 - 1/2 hour delay for T/O because of CO leak within the instrument
3. AOSS - Torque = 2.0 - more silicon grease reqd. Noisy at low level.
4. FL Monitor - ~~lose~~ ^{lose} ~~blue~~ ^{blue} gun? intermittently - display black/red when on decl. bright green on HAAEE.
5. Seadas: Nothing recognizable on FL display. Intermittent on A/c Sinks

* Flt No list for F. Van A480 → A494
 Boscombe Lat 51.163N
 Long -1.743E

Tomorrow N. Sea.

Peroxide: Not available for CAPP.
 MAYDAY call 1510Z

ATC: Shannon boundary not marked on the UK Low Level Map now.
 need to use upper too.

Aircraft: ① crew door warning light intermittent - Fixed preflight
 ② hydraulic fluid leak on taxi; booster pump?
 ③ autopilot - pitches up in descent.

BOTTLE SAMPLERS Log.

Sheet 1 /

Flight No 1479

Date 16/9/96 Operator Dave

Bottle No	Purge Start	Fill start	Fill end	Altitude	Pressure	Comments
Acru P3 B1	12:28:30	12:30:30 12:28:30	12:31:09 12:24:20	600ft	7.2	
Acru P3 B2	12:42:43	12:45:30	12:53:20	2600ft	7.2	
Acru P3 B3	12:54:55	12:56:40	12:57:38	2600	7.2	
Acru P3 B4	12:59:20	13:06:30	13:07:07	2600	7.2	
Acru P3 B5	13:15:30	13:18:00	13:18:30	600ft	7.2	
Acru P3 B6	13:20:00	13:26:50	13:27:25	600ft	7.2	
Acru P3 B7	14:16:13	14:26:14	14:26:52	2600ft	7.2	
Acru P3 B8	14:34:38	14:37:20	14:37:58	4500ft	7.2	
Acru P3 B9	14:40:00	14:47:40	14:48:18	4500	7.2	
Acru P3 B10	14:49:55	15:03:28	15:04:05 15:03:28	4000	7.2	
Acru P3 B11	15:12:23	15:14:20 15:14:23	15:15:06	2600	7.2	
Acru P3 B12	15:15:30	15:23:07	15:23:45	2600	7.2	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A479

Date: 6/9/96

Operator: *myD*

Page 2 of 6

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C			HVPS / 2D-P			REMARKS	
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Conc/cc	Max Size	RcIT	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m ³	Max Size		Habit
120600	8000	0.10											FLO70
120650	8400	0.11	0.04	5									FLO60
120735	3100	0.11											FLO50
120931	40	0.09											4000'
121103	850	0.10	0.08	5									3000'
121235	870	0.10	0.1	5									2000'
121412	980	0.10	1	10									1000'
121516	960	0.10	1	10									500'
121643	1000	0.10	1	10									end of Run 2 @ 500'
122310													Start Run 2 @ 600'
122400	1000	0.09	0.5	5									
122600	970	0.10											
122800	930	0.10	1	5									
123000	770	0.10	1	70									
123200	760	0.09	1	15									
123400	690	0.09	1	10									
123600	610	0.09	1	10									
123700													
124330													end of Run 2
124400	600	0.10	2	10									Start Run 3 @ 2600'
124600	670	0.15	300	35	6	16	50	12					
124800	790	0.16	0.8	10									
125000	540	0.10	0.1	5									
125200	560	0.10											
125400	540	0.10											
125600	40	0.10											
125800	600	0.10											
130000	615	0.10											
130200	500	0.10											
130400	380	0.09											
130600	380	0.09											
130800	440	0.09											
131000	490	0.09											
131200	440	0.10											
131320													
131515													end of Run 3
													Start Run 4 @ 600'

DATE 16 Sep 96

TI MRF A479j

NAV CANAL

AIRFIELD BD

AIRFIELD _____

R/W DS W/V 140/9 TEMP +15 ONH 1023 OFF 1007

R/W DS W/V _____ TEMP _____ ONH 1020 OFF 1004

WX Blue

WX Blue

ATC CL 3327 CEF

ATC CL _____

T/O TIME 105

LAND TIME _____

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG	RUN
1103 ²⁴	135	S	222	182	240	167/21	180		N 50508 W 03094	R1
38 ²⁵									N 49385 W 05520	-
48 ⁴⁴	250	65	257	193	260	168/22	F240		N 49150 W 06261	P1
1216 ⁴³									N 49093 W 07227	-
23 ⁶	248	75	195	182	185	134/27	600		N 49124 W 06580	R2
37 ¹⁰									N 49011 W 08076	-
43 ²⁴	088	80	177	178	187	154/40	2600		N 49566 W 08253	R3
1313 ²⁶									N 49570 W 06133	-
1315 ¹⁵	200	65	196	178	182	122/35	600		N 49153 W 06183	R4
30 ⁴⁴									N 49043 W 07317	-
31 ³⁰	351	38	205	178	175	136/33	1000		N 49092 W 07347	PP1
							5000		N 49264 W 07411	-
							100		N 49554 W 07482	-
							500		N 50030 W 07550	-
							100		N 50230 W 08011	-
							1100		N 51044 W 08007	-
1413 ⁴⁰							50		N 51210 W 08260	-
16 ⁸	239	125	183	180	195	160/37	2600		N 51182 W 08399	R5
31 ¹⁷									N 51053 W 09521	-
34 ⁴⁴	080	90	194	183	198	158/40	4500		N 51066 W 09400	R6
1504 ⁵⁵							4000		N 51329 W 07135	-
07 ²³							500		N 51345 W 07070	P2
12 ²⁵	232	110	179	178	184	155/39	2600		N 51301 W 07337	-R7
1525 ²⁴									N 51196 W 08368	-

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT / LONG	RUN
1528 ²⁰	099	5P	760	180	180	188/33	550		N 51172 W 08870	R3
4.27 ¹³							FR50		N 51127 W 06653	-
5.0 ⁰⁵	195	30	323	240	318	54/50	1480		N 51119 W 06291	R8
1605 ⁰¹									N 51100 W 04305	-

A479 16-SEP-96 14:21:09 033 2 51.22 -9.03 FR P

HDG deg T 239.	SPR mb 921.	PHGT k ft 2.6	TAS knots 181.	TAT C 11.7	DEW C 3.9	WIND deg m/s 161/20
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A479 16-SEP-96 13:08:54 022 Ω 49.25 -6.59 RV P

HDG degT 89.	SPR mb 922.	PHGT kft 2.6	TAS knots 188.	TAT C 10.9	DEW C 3.7	WIND deg m/s 151/17
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CO MR
996
127.50

117.00

OZONE MR
996

49.40

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A479 16-SEP-96 13:10:09 022 Ω 49.26 -6.49 FC P

HDS deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
89.	922.	2.6	188.	11.1	2.0	152/19

CO MR 2047.50 H2O2 MR 1.15
ppb pob

H	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
REF	ECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM	VIDEO	HELP	

A479 16-SEP-96 12:17:15 018 2 49.18 -7.35 FL P

HDG deg 83.	SPR mb 990.	PHGT kft 0.6	TAS knts 187.	TAT C 14.0	DEM C 11.6	WIND deg m/s 138/18
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000 000 000 000 000 000 000 000

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A479 16-SEP-96 11:25:09 013 50.28 -5.24 FL P

HDS deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knts	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
236.	506.	18.0	239.	-15.7	-32.2	171/10

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	PARAS	FREQ	ZOOM			VIDEO	HELP

A479 16-SEP-96 12:25:15 019 49.18 -7.09 FC P

HDG deg	SPR m/s	PHGT kts	TAS knots	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
247.	992.	0.6	186.	13.6	10.7	139/16

FEET HGT 182.16 m CO MR 161.50 PRS H202 MP 0.50 PRS
 0.00 50.00 100.00 150.00 200.00 250.00
 10000.00 8000.00 6000.00 4000.00 2000.00 0.00

H	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SFI FCT CHEM			ZOOM	VIDEO			

A479 16-SEP-96 12:20:48 018 -- 49.22 -7.11 AS P

ASST	SPR	PHGT	TAS	TAT	DEW	WIND
83.	991.	0.6	183.	13.8	10.8	137/18
	ms	kft	knots	C	C	deg m/s

FEET HGT	193.46	m	TEMP	13.33	deg	CO MP	138.50	deg
0.00	33.33	deg	100.00	133.33	133.33	10000.00		

0.00	50.00	100.00	150.00	200.00	250.00	300.00	350.00
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H	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDE	

16 SEP '96 04:49

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A479

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.36.07

A479.TXT

From 18Z 12/ 9/1996 to 15Z 16/ 9/1996

Arrows every 24 hrs

Plotted 28-Oct-1996 13:26

A479 16-SEP-96

P1 FL240-50ft(114849-121640) + Up 100ft-5000ft(133136-133648)

A479 16-SEP-96

Down 5000ft-100ft(133648-134203) + Up 100ft-5000ft(134203-134714)

A479 16-SEP-96

Down 5000ft-100ft(134714-135238) + Up 100ft-FL100(135238-140248)

A479 16-SEP-96

Down FL100-50ft(140248-141349) + P2 5000ft-26000ft(150723-151223)

A479 16-SEP-96

P3 50ft-FL180(152836-154753)

A479 16-SEP-96 R1 FL180 From 110324-113803 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:12

A479 16-SEP-96 R1 FL180 From 110324-113803 Plotted 11-04-1996 17:12

A479 16-SEP-96 R1 FL180 From 110324-113803 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:12

A479 16-SEP-96 R1 FL180 From 110324-113803 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:12

A479 16-SEP-96 R1 FL180 From 110324-113803 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:12

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 2080
Mean 507.089
Standard dev 0.359674
Max value 507.854
Min value 505.842

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 2080
Mean 258.051
Standard dev 0.537113
Max value 258.998
Min value 257.064

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 2080
Mean 239.807
Standard dev 1.88235
Max value 243.624
Min value 236.127

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 2080
Mean 53.6837
Standard dev 3.56506
Max value 66.2709
Min value 46.2801

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 2080
Mean 14.7727
Standard dev 6.44333
Max value 46.0254
Min value 1.00000

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 2080
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 2080
Mean 5470.39
Standard dev 5.24485
Max value 5488.59
Min value 5459.25

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 2080
Mean 50.3582
Standard dev 0.323689
Max value 50.8488
Min value 49.6507

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 2080
Mean -4.73783
Standard dev 0.851291
Max value -3.15240
Min value -5.86529

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2080
Mean 7.33654
Standard dev 3.42376
Max value 13.1953
Min value 2.08807

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2080
Mean -1.63219
Standard dev 0.792386
Max value 0.387848
Min value -3.64634

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2080
Mean -0.359171
Standard dev 0.419095
Max value 1.25681
Min value -1.68543

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 2080
Mean 7.60210
Standard dev 3.32360
Max value 13.4250
Min value 2.48483

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 167.457

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 2080
Mean 123.638
Standard dev 1.28929
Max value 127.386
Min value 120.695

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 235.303

A479 16-SEP-96 P1 FL240-50ft From 114849-121640 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:17

A479 16-SEP-96 P1 FL240-50ft From 114849-121640 Plotted 11-04-1996 17:17

A479 16-SEP-96 P1 FL240-50ft From 114849-121640 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:17

A479 16-SEP-96 Stack1 R2-R4 600/2600ft From 122340-133014 Plotted 11-04-1996 17:27

A479 16-SEP-96 Stack1 R2-R4 600/2600ft From 122340-133014 Plotted 11-06-1996 17:27

A479 16-SEP-96 Stack1 R2-R4 600/2600ft From 122340-133014 Plotted 11-06-1996 17:27

A479 16-SEP-96 Stack1 R2-R4 600/2600ft From 122340-133014 Plotted 11-04-1996 17:27

A479 16-SEP-96 Stack1 R2-R4 600/2600ft From 122340-133014 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:28

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 3995
Mean 959.687
Standard dev 34.6407
Max value 996.746
Min value 921.979

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 3995
Mean 286.004
Standard dev 1.55244
Max value 288.145
Min value 282.380

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 3995
Mean 281.161
Standard dev 3.89090
Max value 286.669
Min value 273.234

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 3995
Mean 48.4837
Standard dev 2.83699
Max value 54.7326
Min value 40.0768

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 3995
Mean 658.321
Standard dev 205.963
Max value 1456.74
Min value 170.671

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)

No of obs 3995
Mean 7.29009
Standard dev 42.5168
Max value 497.048
Min value 0.000000

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 3995
Mean 482.042
Standard dev 307.625
Max value 821.300
Min value 156.321

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 3995
Mean 49.1273
Standard dev 9.021600e-02
Max value 49.2914
Min value 48.9392

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 3995
Mean -7.33185
Standard dev 0.633435
Max value -6.20443
Min value -8.48010

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 3995
Mean 14.0860
Standard dev 3.97502
Max value 21.8734
Min value 4.96674

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 3995
Mean -9.07978
Standard dev 1.78227
Max value -4.60313
Min value -13.1889

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 3995
Mean -0.206037
Standard dev 0.464905
Max value 1.64178
Min value -2.42216

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 3995
Mean 17.1174
Standard dev 2.61283
Max value 22.6745
Min value 10.9355

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 147.194

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 3995
Mean 95.8206
Standard dev 1.61730
Max value 100.143
Min value 90.7196

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 249.743

A479 16-SEP-96 Up 100ft-5000ft From 133136-133648 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:29

A479 16-SEP-96 Up 100ft-5000ft From 133136-133648 Plotted 11-04-1996 17:29

A479 16-SEP-96 Up 100ft-5000ft From 133136-133648 Plotted 11-04-1996 17:29

A479 16-SEP-96 Down 5000ft-100ft From 133648-134203 Plotted 11-06-1996 17:30

A479 16-SEP-96 Down 5000ft-100ft From 133648-134203 Plotted 11-0ct-1996 17:30

A479 16-SEP-96 Down 5000ft-100ft From 133648-134203 Plotted 11-06-1996 17:31

A479 16-SEP-96 Up 100ft-5000ft From 134203-134714 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:32

A479 16-SEP-96 Up 100ft-5000ft From 134203-134714 Plotted 11-01-1996 17:32

A479 16-SEP-96 Up 100ft-5000ft From 134203-134714 Plotted 11-01-1996 17:32

A479 16-SEP-96 Down 5000ft-100ft From 134714-135238 Plotted 11-0ct-1996 17:33

A479 16-SEP-96 Down 5000ft-100ft From 134714-135238 Plotted 11-0ct-1996 17:33

A479 16-SEP-96 Down 5000ft-100ft From 134714-135238 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:33

A479 16-SEP-96 Up 100ft-FL100 From 135238-140248 Plotted 11-0ct-1996 17:36

A479 16-SEP-96 Up 100ft-FL100 From 135238-140248 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:36

A479 16-SEP-96 Up 100ft-FL100 From 135238-140248 Plotted 11-04-1996 17:36

A479 16-SEP-96 Down FL100-50ft From 140248-141349 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:38

A479 16-SEP-96 Down FL100-50ft From 140248-141349 Plotted 11-01-1996 17:38

A479 16-SEP-96 Down FL100-50ft From 140248-141349 Plotted 11-06-1996 17:38

A479 16-SEP-96 Porpoise run From 133136-141349 *Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:45*

A479 16-SEP-96 Porpoise run From 133136-141349 Plotted 11-04-1996 17:45

A479 16-SEP-96 Porpoise run From 133136-141349 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:45

A479 16-SEP-96 Porpoise run From 133136-141349 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:45

A479 16-SEP-96 Porpoise run From 133136-141349 *Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:45*

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean 889.622
 Standard dev 85.4598
 Max value 1012.15
 Min value 696.857

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean 283.460
 Standard dev 3.35889
 Max value 289.048
 Min value 274.734

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean 271.488
 Standard dev 11.8013
 Max value 286.145
 Min value 245.826

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean 52.1757
 Standard dev 4.27082
 Max value 64.9487
 Min value 42.6062

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean 413.873
 Standard dev 320.869
 Max value 1237.57
 Min value 8.00078

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean 0.241048
 Standard dev 2.27553
 Max value 111.943
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean 1116.03
 Standard dev 812.538
 Max value 3047.49
 Min value 9.16472

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean 50.3813
 Standard dev 0.720866
 Max value 51.4257
 Min value 49.1335

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean -7.93598
 Standard dev 0.184624
 Max value -7.56899
 Min value -8.45067

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean 15.2719
 Standard dev 2.40756
 Max value 18.8435
 Min value 7.17767

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean -7.94283
 Standard dev 2.41045
 Max value -3.66614
 Min value -13.8850

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean -6.873668e-02
 Standard dev 1.88532
 Max value 4.07040
 Min value -3.07998

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean 17.4560
 Standard dev 1.79174
 Max value 20.6084
 Min value 11.3492

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 152.521

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 2534
 Mean 99.0416
 Standard dev 4.95958
 Max value 110.676
 Min value 85.9230

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 345.783

A479 16-SEP-96 Stack2 R5-7 2600/5000ft From 141618-152524 Plotted 11-04-1996 17:52

A479 16-SEP-96 Stack2 R5-7 2600/5000ft From 141618-152524 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:53

A479 16-SEP-96 Stack2 R5-7 2600/5000ft From 141618-152524 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:53

A479 16-SEP-96 Stack2 R5-7 2600/5000ft From 141618-152524 Plotted 11-04-1996 17:53

A479 16-SEP-96 Stack2 R5-7 2600/5000ft From 141618-152524 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:53

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 4141
Mean 889.399
Standard dev 30.0971
Max value 925.347
Min value 842.300

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 4141
Mean 283.695
Standard dev 0.979724
Max value 286.055
Min value 281.398

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 4141
Mean 269.880
Standard dev 7.33176
Max value 283.446
Min value 256.319

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 4141
Mean 51.2004
Standard dev 5.55888
Max value 63.3985
Min value 36.1190

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 4141
Mean 280.349
Standard dev 267.225
Max value 1587.14
Min value 3.00010

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 4141
Mean 2.01032
Standard dev 23.7140
Max value 447.320
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 4141
Mean 1089.89
Standard dev 278.024
Max value 1531.44
Min value 758.845

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 4141
Mean 51.3211
Standard dev 0.143313
Max value 51.6010
Min value 51.0648

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 4141
Mean -8.49101
Standard dev 0.820752
Max value -7.08612
Min value -9.88672

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 4141
Mean 19.0176
Standard dev 1.54100
Max value 22.7604
Min value 15.4143

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 4141
Mean -7.18261
Standard dev 1.52346
Max value -3.99429
Min value -12.4403

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 4141
Mean -0.185724
Standard dev 0.486653
Max value 1.66556
Min value -1.90257

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 4141
Mean 20.3862
Standard dev 1.53543
Max value 24.2346
Min value 16.6700

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 159.309

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 4141
Mean 99.3814
Standard dev 3.01296
Max value 104.268
Min value 90.6964

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 77.6305

A479 16-SEP-96 P2 5000ft-2600ft From 150723-151223 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:53

A479 16-SEP-96 P2 5000ft-2600ft From 150723-151223 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:53

A479 16-SEP-96 P2 5000ft-2600ft From 150723-151223 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:53

A479 16-SEP-96 P3 50ft-FL180 From 152836-154753 Plotted 11-04-1996 17:55

A479 16-SEP-96 P3 50ft-FL180 From 152836-154753 Plotted 11-04-1996 17:55

A479 16-SEP-96 P3 50ft-FL180 From 152836-154753 Plotted 11-01-1996 17:55

A479 16-SEP-96 R8 FL180 From 155006-160501 Plotted 11-01-1996 17:56

A479 16-SEP-96 R8 FL180 From 155006-160501 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:56

A479 16-SEP-96 R8 FL180 From 155006-160501 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:56

A479 16-SEP-96 R8 FL180 From 155006-160501 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:56

A479 16-SEP-96 R8 FL180 From 155006-160501 *Plotted 11-Oct-1996 17:56*

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 896
Mean 507.591
Standard dev 0.222962
Max value 507.960
Min value 506.792

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 896
Mean 258.864
Standard dev 0.770992
Max value 260.039
Min value 257.388

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 896
Mean 238.701
Standard dev 1.40135
Max value 241.886
Min value 236.568

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 896
Mean 54.2766
Standard dev 4.32972
Max value 70.1488
Min value 48.2403

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 896
Mean 12.4377
Standard dev 6.51975
Max value 44.0186
Min value 1.00003

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 896
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 896
Mean 5463.08
Standard dev 3.24862
Max value 5474.73
Min value 5457.71

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 896
Mean 51.1890
Standard dev 7.918909e-03
Max value 51.1988
Min value 51.1705

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 896
Mean -5.51817
Standard dev 0.584945
Max value -4.50072
Min value -6.52116

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 896
Mean 12.1448
Standard dev 1.96994
Max value 16.2368
Min value 7.59726

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 896
Mean -4.16909
Standard dev 1.84124
Max value -0.534676
Min value -7.33040

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 896
Mean 0.221838
Standard dev 0.627897
Max value 1.91040
Min value -0.917305

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 896
Mean 12.8995
Standard dev 2.39758
Max value 17.2228
Min value 7.87191

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 161.054

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 896
Mean 162.876
Standard dev 0.931758
Max value 164.773
Min value 157.605

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 91.2839

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems. Pitch and yaw are only displayed for flight A480, where specific manoeuvres were used to test the response of the NO_x inlets.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.
- **FWVS Dew point:** dew point calculated by use of the Lyman- α spectroscopic instrument “the fluorescence water vapour sensor”.

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP:** The Passive Cavity Aerosol Sampling Probe counts number concentrations (number per cm³) of particles in 15 channels spaced pseudo-logarithmically over the diameter range 0.10 μ m to 3.00 μ m, to provide a particle size distribution over this range.
- **FSSP:** The Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe is used to measure water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47.0 μ m diameter (cloud droplets). It has four range settings, each of which is divided into 15 size channels.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **CO:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Stefan Kessler (KFA Julich).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (raw data). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Stefan Kessler (KFA Julich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Modelled peroxide:** hydrogen peroxide concentrations as estimated from the concentrations of ozone and water vapour concentrations according to the following algorithm. The model is used in flight and is included in this data summary for individual scientists assessment of the use of algorithms for the purpose of in flight planning. Contact Brian Bandy, Claire Reeves (UEA, Norwich) or Dave Tiddeman (UK Met. Office) for details.

$$H_2O_2 = (k_3 j_4 [O_3] [H_2O]) / (k_5 [M] (j_6 + k_7 + [OH] k_8))$$

where k_3 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + H_2O \rightarrow 2OH$

k_5 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + M \rightarrow O(^3P) + M$

k_8 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $OH + H_2O_2 \rightarrow H_2O + HO_2$

k_7 is the first order loss due to dry deposition. However, as the boundary layer is difficult to define, this term has been ignored for the time being.

j_4 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O_3 + hv \rightarrow O(^1D) + O_2$

j_6 is the rate coefficient for reaction: $H_2O_2 + hv \rightarrow OH + OH$

j_4 , j_6 and $[OH]$, calculated by a 2D model, are dependent upon latitude and time of year.

- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data recorded as bits. NB this instrument has a long time delay *ca.* 12 minutes. Instrument scientist: Laura Cardenas (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters were not recorded on MRF's data recording system and are therefore not available as part of this data summary. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **PAN ECGC's:** Data are not included in this report but will be made available at a later date. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office).

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